

Analysis and Optimization of CVMFS caches on LxPlus

Author:

Jakub Ogradowczyk

Supervisors:

Valentin Volkl, valentin.volkl@cern.ch

Steve Traylen, steve.traylen@cern.ch

August 15th, 2024

I. INTRODUCTION

At CERN, **Lxplus (Linux Public Login User Service)** is a general-purpose, shared pool of Linux machines widely used by researchers and engineers for tasks such as data processing, simple computations, and interaction with other CERN services (e.g. EOS, AFS, OpenStack). On average, about 1,000 people use it each day. Each Lxplus box comes with a pre-configured Alma 9 system and provides users with access to a host featuring 9 cores and 30 GB of RAM. The configuration of each of the boxes is deployed using the **puppet** tool.

Software distribution on Lxplus is handled through **CVMFS (CernVM File System)**, a POSIX, read-only file system that operates in user space as a FUSE module developed by the CVMFS team from the SFT group. The service allows users to access the latest versions of experiment software without needing to install or update packages locally.

Fig. 1: CVMFS interaction diagram

CVMFS works by mounting images of remote repositories under the `/cvmfs` directory (ex. `/cvmfs/sft.cern.ch/` when needed). After the user tries to read a file from one of the repositories, the FUSE kernel module forwards the request to the CVMFS2 process running in the user space. The file is then fetched from the remote repository and stored

in the local cache. Subsequent accesses to the file will bypass the fetching process and retrieve it directly from the cache (local storage) which greatly decreases the access time.

The CVMFS configuration on Lxplus is, same as other tools, deployed using puppet. By default, the cache size is set to 25GB, shared between all the repositories. When the cache size exceeds this limit, half of the files are removed based on how long it has been since they were last accessed.

The aim of this project was to gather data on the usage patterns of CVMFS on Lxplus, explore this data, test hypotheses proposed by the development team, and enhance the existing monitoring infrastructure.

II. DATA GATHERING

A key objective of the project was to collect data on CVMFS usage across the Lxplus cluster. To achieve this, I used **wassh** - a parallel SSH tool that enables command execution across all hosts in the cluster. The approach I've chosen was running a bash script on each host, which executed a Python program and saved the output to a file in the eos service directory.

There are a couple of tools designed to help probe the usage data out of the local CVMFS service. Most notably, the `cvmfs_talk` tool allows us to communicate with the running **CVMFS2** process through the usage of a few internal commands. The ones I've utilized in this project are:

```
> cvmfs_talk <command>
* cache size - gets current size of files in the cache
* cache list - gets the list of files in the cache
* internal affairs - gets the list of internal counters and statistics
* ...
```

Listing 1: Examples of `cvmfs_talk` subcommands

Another method for collecting usage data and internal counters is through extended file attributes. Each mounted repository stores metadata in its extended attributes, which can be retrieved using Linux utilities. For example:

```
> getfattr -d /cvmfs/sft.cern.ch
# file: cvmfs/sft.cern.ch/
...
user.revision="30496"
user.timestamp_last_ioerr="0"
user.uptime="463"
user.useddirp="0"
user.usedfd="1"
...
```

Listing 2: Example of interaction with extended attributes

For the purposes of the project, I've developed a python library that allows for easy communication with the CVMFS2 process. The library provides a wrapper around the `cvmfs_talk` tool that allows for easy execution of commands and parsing of the output. The bulk of library's functionality relies on the `run_cvmfs_talk_command` function:

```
1 def run_cvmfs_talk_command(repo_name, *commands):
2     command = ["cvmfs_talk", "-i", repo_name] + [c for c in commands]
3     result = subprocess.run(command, stdout=subprocess.PIPE)
4
5     return result
```

Listing 3: The `run_cvmfs_talk_command` function

The rest of the library consists of functions that, through wrappers built around the previously mentioned tools, collect and parse the data into serializable objects. The specific data I focused on included:

1. The list of currently mounted repositories
2. Size of the cache (local storage)
3. Cache revisions – using extended attributes
4. List of files in the cache
5. File to repository mapping
6. Size of files in the cache
7. Startup of the **ROOT** program

Gathering the list of mounted repositories

The list of mounted repositories can be easily obtained using the Linux `mount -l` command. The output can then be parsed using a regular expression (`"/cvmfs/([^\]+)"`). Below is the python code:

```

1 def get_cvmfs_mounted_repos():
2     command = "mount -l | grep cvmfs2"
3     result = subprocess.run(command, shell=True, stdout=subprocess.PIPE)
4
5     lines = result.stdout.decode("utf-8").splitlines()
6     repos = []
7     for line in lines:
8         m = re.search("/cvmfs/([^\ ]+)", line)
9         repos.append(m.group(1))
10
11     return repos

```

Listing 4: The function for getting the list of mounted repositories

Gathering the size of the cache

Size of the cache can be obtained directly from the `cvmfs_talk` tool. We only need to parse the output of the command which, as previously, can be done using a regular expression (`"\\((([0-9]+))"`).

```

1 def get_cvmfs_cache_size(repo_name):
2     result = run_cvmfs_talk_command(repo_name, "cache", "size")
3     m = re.findall("\\((([0-9]+)", str(result.stdout))
4     if not m:
5         throw_err("Could not find pattern for cache and pinned size.")
6
7     return (m[0], m[1])

```

Listing 5: The function for getting the current size of the cache

The function returns two values as a tuple. That is because the `cvmfs_talk cache size` command returns two separate numbers - the overall size of the cache and the size taken up by the the pinned files.

Gathering cache revisions

In order to get the local cache revision for each of the mounted repositories, we need to access the extended attributes. To accomplish that, I've decided to use the `xattr` python library. The list of attributes is returned as a `dict` data structure. The name of the attribute containing the revision number is `"user.revision"`.

```

1 def get_extended_attributes(repo_name):
2     full_path = "/cvmfs/" + repo_name
3     attribute_names = xattr.listxattr(full_path)
4     attributes = {}
5     for attribute_name in attribute_names:
6         name = (
7             attribute_name
8             if isinstance(attribute_name, str)
9             else attribute_name.decode("utf-8")
10        )
11        attributes[name] = xattr.getxattr(full_path, name).decode("utf-8")
12
13    return attributes

```

Listing 6: The function that gets extended attributes of a file as a dict

Gathering the list of files in the cache

Similarly to the size of the cache, this information is provided by the `cvmfs_talk` tool using the `cache list` sub-command. In this case, the return type is a set since the list we are getting out of `cvmfs_talk` contains paths relative to the repositories, without the repository name. For the simplicity of other operations, we won't to have no duplicates in the final list, which could be the case if two repositories contained a file with the same relative path.

```

1 def get_cvmfs_cached_files(repo_name):
2     result = run_cvmfs_talk_command(repo_name, "cache", "list")
3     lines = result.stdout.decode("utf-8").splitlines()
4     files = set()
5
6     for line in lines:
7         if line.startswith("/"):
8             files.add(line)
9             continue
10        prefix = "Part of "
11        if line.startswith(prefix):
12            files.add(line[len(prefix) :])
13
14    return files

```

Listing 7: Function that returns the list of files in the cache

Mapping file names to repositories

As discussed in the previous point, there is no trivial way to find out which remote repository did a file in the cache come from, since

1. The cache is shared between all of the repositories
2. The `cvmfs_talk cache list` command returns paths relative to the repository

Because of that, the easiest solution I came up with was to use a brute force algorithm that one by one prefixes the relative file path with the name of a repository and checks whether such a path exists using the `os.path.exists(-path)` function.

```

1 def find_repo_for_file_brute_force(file, mounted_repos):
2     for repo in mounted_repos:
3         path = f"/cvmfs/{repo}/{file}"
4         if os.path.exists(path):
5             return repo
6
7     return None

```

Listing 8: Function that by brute force, finds which repository does a file belong to

There are a couple of things to note about this approach.

I : The way I gather the list of files removes duplicate entries. This means that if two or more repositories have a file at the same relative path, the code will only detect one of them, depending on the order of the list returned by the `mount -l` command. This obviously leads to discrepancies between the actual state of the system and the data we collect.

However, since repositories are frequently unmounted (in the current configuration, a repository gets dismounted after one minute of not being used) and the remote image can be updated with a new revision at any time, it is impossible to capture the true state of the system. By the time we take a snapshot, both the remote and local environments have likely changed since the time the file was saved in the cache.

Additionally, instances where this occurs are quite rare and account for a marginal fraction of the total files in the cache (there are on average 35,143 files in the cache). As a result, this has little impact on the overall accuracy of the measurement, and attempting to account for this would unnecessarily increase the code complexity without a significant gain in precision.

II : For most of the data I've gathered I was checking the files against the list of currently mounted repositories which I got from the `get_cvmfs_mounted_repos()` function. That means that some of the files will not be matched against any repository in the list. In that case, the algorithm returns `None`. Those files make up around 23.5% of the overall cache. There are a few reasons why I haven't been checking against the list of all repositories:

1. No such list exists
2. The time would grow linearly with the number of checked repos
3. With time, the list could quite possibly go out of date

After two months of gathering data, I've ended up with a list of repositories which have been mounted over that period and the number of unique ones turned out to be 66. Because I didn't have access to that list at the beginning, I was unable to check against it.

III : This approach is quite slow, as previously mentioned - there are on average 35,143 files in the cache and 10 repositories mounted at each time. In the worst case we will have a time complexity of $O(nm)$ where n - number of files, m - number of repositories. In practice, this process has usually taken around 2 minutes for the whole cluster depending on the load of the system and other factors. This amount of time may seem like a lot, but because we do not want to run the data gathering too often, it falls within reasonable bounds. Final version of the data gathering tool checks the full list for files which were not matched to the list of mounted repositories. Due to linear complexity of the algorithm, checking against the list of all known repositories is around 6.6 times slower ($m = 66$ vs $m = 10$) but because only around 25% of files come from unmounted repositories, that cost is not as great.

Gathering the file sizes

Another piece of data I was interested in was the size of files in the cache. Now that we have the full paths of the files in the cache it seems to be trivial and boils down to `os.path.getsize(file_path)`. However, as noted previously, the algorithm checks each file against the list of currently mounted repositories and, because the repositories get unmounted, almost a quarter of the files end up without a match. Later versions of the algorithm had mostly

eliminated that issue by checking the unmounted files against the list of all found repositories but the data gathered before that had a lot of file which were unmapped.

Another thing to note is that some of the files end up being deleted in a new revision of a repository. In that case, this algorithm is unable to find the size of a file. An alternative, and possibly better approach, that solves that issue, is checking the sizes straight from the physical files existing on the disk without accessing them through the CVMFS file system. The problem with that solution, is that the names of those files are their content hashes and in order to map them to the actual file names, I would have to first read the database that CVMFS stored locally which contains that information. In the end, I decided to stick with the first approach as I already have implemented it and the drawbacks weren't big enough to migrate to the second one.

```

1 def get_file_size(file_name, repo, all_repos):
2     if not file_name.startswith('/'):
3         file_name = '/' + file_name
4
5     file_path = f"/cvmfs/{repo}{file_name}"
6
7     if repo is not None and os.path.exists(file_path):
8         return os.path.getsize(file_path)
9
10    repo = find_repo_for_file_brute_force(file_name, all_repos)
11    file_path = f"/cvmfs/{repo}{file_name}"
12    if os.path.exists(file_path):
13        return os.path.getsize(file_path)
14
15    return None

```

Listing 9: Function that finds a file size for a given file and repository

Measuring ROOT startup

Lastly, I wanted to measure the startup of the ROOT program. ROOT is an open-source data analysis framework developed by the SFT group (the group to which the CVMFS belongs to). It is widely used by researchers and data analysts for things like statistical analysis and data visualization. Because it's such a powerful and versatile tool, it's installation grows to quite a size. On Lxplus, ROOT is distributed using CVMFS and has a reputation of taking quite a bit of time on it's first startup. Measuring the state of the environment when ROOT is run would allow to possibly find some optimizations in the future. The methodology I've ended up employing was as such:

1. Save the state of CVMFS before running ROOT
2. Run root across cluster and measure startup time
3. Save the CVMFS state again
4. Run root for the second time and measure the startup again

The program I've used for the measurements creates a data frame with a 100 entries, defines a new column containing random numbers from a uniform distribution, creates a 1D histogram, and finally draws the histogram using `DrawClone()`.

```

1 ROOT::RDataFrame rdf(100);
2 auto rdf_x = rdf.Define("x", []() {
3     return gRandom->Rndm();
4 });
5 auto h = rdf_x.Histo1D("x");
6 h->DrawClone();

```

Listing 10: An example ROOT program used for startup measurements

The final bash command was `root -q -b -e 'ROOT::RDataFrame rdf(100); auto rdf_x = rdf.Define("x", [](){ return gRandom->Rndm(); }); auto h = rdf_x.Histo1D("x"); h->DrawClone();'`

III. EXPANDING THE MONITORING INFRASTRUCTURE

With a system as complex as Lxplus and over a thousand people using it each day, it's very important to carefully monitor the state of the system at all times. The monitoring infrastructure consists of four parts:

1. data gathering
2. data storage
3. data visualization
4. alerting

For the purposes of data visualization and alerting, the IT department uses a tool called **Grafana**. Grafana allows for an easy way to create dashboards with different visualizations of the collected data and provides an easy way to setup alarms if the newest data doesn't fit within the safe parameters. Long term storage is done using **InfluxDB**. The data gathering is done using a plethora of different of tools. The one I was mostly interested in was **collectd** which is used for the collection of data on CVMFS.

The existing infrastructure

Previously, the monitored data consisted of the average mount time of a repository and the number of cache cleanups over the past 24 hours. If the average mount time spiked for an extended period, it would indicate that the connection between the cluster and the remote server was likely overloaded. The number of cleanups also had an alarm set and was typically triggered by suspicious user activity or misuse of the provided tools. A recent example involved a user running the following command:

```
grep --color=auto -r POG /cvmfs/cms.cern.ch/alma8_aarch64_gcc11
/cvmfs/cms.cern.ch/alma8_amd64_gcc1
```

Which resulted in all the recursively greped files being fetched one by one, overloading the cache multiple times and finally setting the alarm off.

Fig. 2: A screenshot picturing an average mount time plot in grafana

Fig. 3: A screenshot picturing a number of clean ups plot in grafana

Adding the monitoring of cache revisions

One potential scenario, which occurred recently, is when one of the nodes contains a repository that significantly lags behind the newest revision on the remote server. This can happen if the CVMFS process, for some reason, is unable to connect to the remote server and therefore is unable to update. Monitoring cache revisions helps detect such cases notify the admins of the issue.

Adding the revision monitoring to the existing pipeline turned out to be quite straightforward. There already exists a CMVFS plugin for the collectd system, created and maintained by my supervisor Steve. The plugin adds functionality needed to scrape selected extended attributes of mounted repositories. Adding cache revisions was as simple as adding another attribute name to the collectd configuration in puppet.

Fig. 4: A screenshot from grafana of the newly added max diff from latest revision

Fig. 5: A screenshot from grafana of the newly added max diff from latest revision without unpacked and lhcbdev

One thing of note is that the repositories `unpacked.cern.ch` and `lhcbdev.cern.ch` tend to quite often be left behind the newest revision. That is due to the nature of those repositories, their purpose is distributing container images through CVMFS and therefore are updated very frequently.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Over the course of my internship, I gathered over 50 GB worth of data. While there are of course many uses of the data which I didn't have time to explore during the course of this project, I have made a few observations which can be seen below along with the visualizations I used for data analysis.

Fig. 6: A histogram representing the distribution of ROOT startup time on the first run and the second run

As shown in Fig. 6, the startup time of ROOT is significantly reduced (by around 4 times), when running it a second time. This behavior is expected, as during the first run, CVMFS needs to fetch a lot of files from the remote server. On the second run, these files are already present in the local cache, which results in a much lower access time.

The rest of the data gathered on ROOT startup can possibly be used in the future to find ways to optimize CVMFS for such cases. One of the considered solutions is bundling files in a single GET request instead of requesting them separately. In that case, the list of files fetched by ROOT on startup can be helpful in during the process of testing out this optimization.

File sizes distribution

Fig. 7: The distribution of files sizes found in the cache

Files smaller than 1MB make up over 93.8% of all files in the cache, files smaller than 1KB make up 26.2%. The average file size is 709KB while the median is 4.5KB. There are also a few other interesting observations that can be made about those plots.

I : One thing to notice about the distribution histogram is a few spikes below the 1KiB line. The first, and largest one of these spikes, constitutes around 1.45% of all files and occurs at exactly 41B. Those files come from the cms.cern.ch repository and are almost exclusively git files. A few examples include /cvmfs/cms.cern.ch/cmssw.git.daily/refs/pull/35741/head or /cvmfs/cms.cern.ch/cmssw.git.daily/refs/pull/30598/merge.

Most of the other spikes also come from cms.cern.ch and are most commonly data files used for simulations in tools like Geant4. One such example: /cvmfs/cms.cern.ch/share/cms/data-MagneticField-Interpolation/V01-01-00/MagneticField/Interpolation/data/grid_160812_3_8t/s10/grid.1377.bin.

II : Another thing of note, on the CDF plot we can see a few outliers past the 1GiB line. Due to the way that CVMFS works currently, those files should be split into smaller parts. In theory, there should be no file bigger than 100MB. In the future, this behavior could be investigated. The biggest one of these files is 35.3GB. That size is greater than the configured 25GB of maximum size for the cache. The reason why this file was found in one of the caches, is that CVMFS has a feature which allows it to pull only part of a file in case it happens to be overly big.

Per repository statistics

Fig. 8: The distribution of file counts found in the cache

As can be seen on Fig. 8, the distribution of percentages tends to stay stable over time. The means that we don't see any significant differences each day between the measurements. Another thing to note is that almost a quarter of all files belong to an unmounted repository. As expected, the most popular repositories are cms.cern.ch, atlas.cern.ch and sft.cern.ch.

Fig. 9: The distribution of file sizes found in the cache

Once again, on Fig. 9 we can see that the unmounted files constitute the biggest part of the split. The three most popular repositories are also the same, albeit in different order. While cms.cern.ch made up on average 31.0% of all files in the cache, those files only take up about 18.6% of the size. This observation is in line with what we have noted about Fig. 7 - most of the spikes in the file count distribution come from the cms.cern.ch repository, but are of a relatively small size (less than 1KB). At the same time, sft.cern.ch has far fewer files overall but individually they are bigger and so they take up more space in the cache overall.

Cache similarity

Fig. 10: A histogram representing the distribution of percentages of files shared between two random boxes

The distribution shown in Fig. 10 represents the percentage of files that are shared between two randomly selected boxes. The distribution is heavily skewed to the left, with the probability density mostly concentrated below 30%. This result tells us that a relatively big percentage of files (around 10%) occurs quite frequently throughout the cluster.

Fig. 11: A histogram representing the distribution of percentages of files shared between all boxes

Taking the previous measurement a step further, I've checked how many files on average occur in *all* of the boxes at the same time. Within all the data I've gathered, the answer was at most 4. That means that despite some files being quite common, there are barely any that occur in every single box at one time. If the numbers for this and the previous metric were sufficiently high, introduction of a cache shared between all boxes could be considered. However, considering this data, we can tell that such a solution wouldn't bring any improvement.

V. CONCLUSION

During the course of the project, I have gathered over 50GB of data which can be used in the future for sanity checking, optimization propositions or bug hunting. The data has already shown a few abnormalities within the service in the Lxplus environment which can at some point be further investigated. The code used for data gathering and visualizations has been packaged as a python 3 library. The current monitoring infrastructure also has been expanded to include cache revisions.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would first like to thank my supervisors, Steve and Valentin, for giving me this opportunity and for their guidance throughout my internship. I would also like to express my gratitude to Kristina Gunne and Fariza Oulashova for organizing the CERN openlab program and ensuring everything ran smoothly.